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**ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE CONTEXT OF REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT
AND INDUSTRY-SPECIFIC FEATURES**

This article explores the development of theoretical and methodological foundations for entrepreneurship management, taking into account regional and industry-specific characteristics. The relevance of this research stems from the need to overcome spatial disparities and enhance the competitiveness of regional economies in the face of global challenges. The aim of this study is to develop a conceptual framework for improving the effectiveness of entrepreneurship management, integrating theoretical approaches in the fields of regional development and industry-specific economics. The study utilizes methods of systemic and comparative analysis, conceptual modeling, and expert assessment. It also provides an overview of the evolution of theories of entrepreneurship, regional development, and industry organization. Original definitions of key concepts, such as «entrepreneurial aspects of regional development,» «industry resilience,» and «regional entrepreneurship policy mechanisms,» are offered. The main result of the study is a conceptual model of a cyclical governance mechanism linking external challenges, institutional support, a monitoring system, a framework for adaptation measures, and the implementation of entrepreneurship support tools in the context of regional development and industry-specific characteristics with feedback. The scientific novelty lies in the synthesis of interdisciplinary approaches and the structuring of the governance process into a unified, self-regulating framework. The practical significance of the model lies in its adaptability by regional governments for the development and adjustment of entrepreneurship support policies.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, regional development, industry-specific characteristics, theoretical aspects, governance mechanism, efficiency, regional policy, cluster, resilience.

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